

CHATBOTS AS CONVERSATIONAL AGENTS AND CONSUMER BRAND ENGAGEMENT IN THE UK RETAIL INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

The research explores the role of chatbots as conversational agents in enhancing consumer brand engagement within the UK retail industry. As artificial intelligence continues to evolve, chatbots have become integral to customer service, offering 24/7 availability, cost-efficiency, and scalability. The study aims to assess how chatbots influence key brand engagement metrics, including customer satisfaction, loyalty, and emotional connection. A qualitative methodology using telephone interviews was employed to gather insights from various UK retail sectors.

Findings suggest that chatbots significantly boost customer satisfaction by providing quick, consistent, and personalized responses. This efficiency often leads to higher brand loyalty, with repeat purchases and positive word-of-mouth being key outcomes. Chatbots also contribute to emotional connections with customers by simulating human interactions, which fosters trust and engagement. However, limitations such as the absence of human empathy and evolving technology mean that chatbots are most effective when integrated with traditional customer service.

In conclusion, while chatbots play a crucial role in enhancing brand engagement and operational efficiency in UK retail, their effectiveness is contingent on proper deployment and continued technological advancements. Further research is recommended to explore chatbot usage across different regions and industries and to assess long-term impacts on consumer behavior.

Keywords: Chatbots, UK Retail Industry, Conversational Agents, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Customer Brand Engagement

Cite this Article: Dr Lasta Dangol and Dr Farhan Rind, Chatbots as Conversational Agents and Consumer Brand Engagement in The UK Retail Industry, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(5), 2024, pp. 67-78.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_5/IJM_15_05_004.pdf

1.0. INTRODUCTION

The days when talking directly with service staff as the only option for customer service have long gone. Currently, the interactions with customers are frequently dealt with by automated system managed by artificial intelligence which is well-known as chatbots (Bock et al., 2020). Chatbot has become increasingly popular recently under the robust development of artificial intelligence and other technologies. Meanwhile, the more frequent Internet interactivity and familiarity with technology have encouraged customers to pursue advanced and personalized customer service which could be brought about by chatbots. Indeed, chatbots have witnessed a significant development recently from \$2.6 billion of market size in 2019 to \$9.4 billion in 2024 which could also be regarded as the segment with the fastest growth rate (Nguyen, 2020).

Such impressive growth rate of chatbots has transformed the communication channels between retailers and customers (Olmez, 2018). Chatbots could alternate human service agents and function as conversational agents for retailers to communicate with their customers (Chen et al., 2021).

Previous papers have taken insight into different types of chatbots as well as their impacts on the customers' response (Mende et al., 2019) or the influential determinants affecting the acceptance and adoption of chatbots by users (Xu et al., 2020). Nevertheless, past papers mainly paid attention to the technology itself without focusing enough into the value of chatbots from the perspective of customers. Therefore, in this paper, the researcher has decided to pay attention to the concept of chatbots as conversational agents and take a look at the role of chatbots in enhancing consumer brand engagement in the retail industry of the UK.

1.1 Research Aims

The aim of this research is to comprehensively assess the impact of chatbots on brand engagement metrics, including customer satisfaction, loyalty, and emotional connection.

1.2 Research Objectives

1. To Measure the impact of chatbots on customer satisfaction levels to traditional Customer service channels
2. To Investigate the correlation between the introduction of chatbots and changes in Brand loyalty
3. To explore the emotional response of customers towards interacting with chatbots
4. To compare the effectiveness of chatbots in enhancing brand engagement metrics across UK retail industry.

1.3 Research Questions

1. How does the introduction of chatbots affect customer satisfaction levels compared to traditional customer service channels?
2. What is the relationship between the use of chatbots and changes in brand loyalty metrics, such as repeat purchases and likelihood of recommending the brand?
3. In what ways do chatbots contribute to fostering emotional connections with users?
4. How does the performance of chatbots in enhancing brand engagement metrics compare across UK retail industry?

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Chatbots as Conversational Agent

The boom in technology based on artificial intelligence (AI) has drawn heavy attention from both practitioners and scholars. Chatbots, in this paper, is one of the applications of AI which aids the communication between companies and their customers via a computer application which could use natural language (Khanna et al., 2015). Starting from a simple rule-driven technology (such as ELIZA), chatbots have evolved to a technology which could use natural language via the development of artificial intelligence and machine learning. Under the natural language process, chatbots are enabled to identify the intent of users' input and provide output by actions accordingly.

2.2. Chatbots and Consumer Brand Engagement

Previously, various research into chatbots have paid more attention into the prediction of acceptance and use of chatbots as technology. However, the role of chatbots adoption in improving consumer brand engagement has still needed further model in order to be understood.

Indeed, it is worth noticing that the quality of service could be evaluated by customers in every touchpoint across their journey comprising of those managed by human agents and chatbots at the same times. If the customers are satisfied with the service, they will definitely be more engaged to the brand. Service quality in the model by Parasuraman et al (1988) including five determinants namely tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. Among those, chatbots could definitely satisfy the responsiveness determinant because chatbots as an automated technology under the aid of AI could be always willing to help and provide prompt responses to inquiries of customers. In comparison with human agents, chatbots have higher competitive advantages in responsiveness due to its ability to provide real-time and instant responses (Chen et al, 2021). In addition to that, chatbots are able to deal with a large volume of inquiries which enables the scalability of customer interaction of any organization. Being designed to deliver prompt, accurate, and cost-effective responses to large volume of customers, chatbots does not improve the engagement of the customers only but also the general operational efficiency of organizations (Hussain, Sianaki and Ababneh, 2019; Adamopoulou and Moussiades, 2020).

The potential benefits of chatbots as a conversational agent to improve customer engagement such as their cost-effectiveness, 24/7 responsiveness and scalability are undeniable. However, Sangroya (2017) highlighted some disadvantages of chatbots which should be taken into consideration by organizations such as the privacy concerns, inadequate human touch, and scripted interactions.

Regardless of the mentioned disadvantages of chatbots, the proper deployment of chatbots could help to leverage customers' data which will then aids to deliver highly-personalized content as well as proactive engagement of customers (Vijayakumar, 2024).

2.3. Chatbots in the Retail Industry

In the retail industry, chatbots are proving its significant role in ensuring the quality of customer service. It is more frequently for retailers to adopt chatbots in their marketing campaigns and engage with their consumers. With the appropriate approach and adoption, it is possible for retailers to improve customers' experiences and boost their revenue via chatbots while saving money and time. Numerous giants in the retail industry such as Amazon, Walmart, Alibaba, Sephora, Unilever, Tesco, etc. have adopted chatbots in order to ensure higher customer engagement (Alibaba.com, 2023; Webretailer, 2024).

Chatbots help to collect and analyse data via the conversations with customers which assists retailers in better understanding customers' preferences and needs. Data from conversations collected via chatbots along with the use of advanced analytics could help retailers predict the behaviours of customers through which delivering suitable marketing messages and providing necessary customized offers. In the era where customers demand hyper-personalized and prompt service, the old-fashioned way of communication and marketing are proved to be inadequate. This fact is even suitable for the retail industry whose volume of customers are excessively large. Thus, the scalability of chatbots to large volume of customers promptly and cost-effectively is considered as a big advantage for chatbots.

Research gap on the effectiveness of chatbots in enhancing brand engagement. The research gap concerning the effectiveness of chatbots in enhancing brand engagement within the UK retail industry stems from a lack of comprehensive empirical studies that specifically focus on this dynamic. While there exists a growing body of literature on chatbots and their utility in customer service and sales support functions, there is a notable dearth of research investigating their impact on brand engagement metrics such as customer satisfaction, loyalty, and emotional connection. Additionally, existing studies predominantly originate from other geographic regions or generalize findings across industries, failing to provide nuanced insights into the unique context of the UK retail landscape. As a result, there is a clear need for empirical research that is specific to the UK retail sector to explain how chatbots affect interactions between consumers and brands and to find the best ways to use these conversational agents to increase brand engagement.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Methods

This section describes the study and data collecting approach used to assess the function of chatbots as conversational agents and customer brand engagement in the UK's retail industry. The study sought to learn about customer views, experiences, and interactions with Chabot's, as well as their influence on brand engagement (Rajasekar, Philominathan & Chinnathambi, 2013). To achieve these goals, a qualitative research technique was used, which included telephone interviews with people drawn from various areas of the UK retail market. The flexibility and ability of qualitative research to elucidate underlying motives and perspectives made it the most suitable method for analyzing the complex nature of these relationships (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2007).

3.2 Interpretivism Research Philosophy

Using an interpretivist research philosophy, this study investigates customer's views of Chabot's and their influence on interaction with retail companies in the United Kingdom. Recognizing the impact of social and cultural settings, the study utilizes qualitative approaches such as phone interviews and thematic analysis to identify the many meanings people give to Chabot interactions and how they form their impressions of companies (Flick, 2018). It recognizes many legitimate realities and opinions by contextualizing the study inside real-world consumer-brand interactions, providing a nuanced investigation of the delicate role Chabot's play in influencing current retail experiences via the prism of human perception (Ryan, 2018).

A meticulous participant selection was essential to capturing the rich diversity of customer opinions and experiences inside the UK retail industry. Participants were carefully selected using purposive sampling from a wide range of the UK retail sector to ensure representation across demographic segments, purchasing habits, and retail preferences.

This all-encompassing strategy sought to include a wide range of perspectives and insights into the field of Chabot-mediated brand interaction (Leedy & Ormrod, 2005).

3.3 Data Collection Technique (Telephonic interviews)

The most effective method for obtaining participants honest and thorough narrative was through telephone interviews. This approach was chosen because of its intrinsic closeness, which gives participants the freedom to speak honestly about their experiences while simultaneously enabling researchers to follow the contours of the conversation and delve further into recurrent topics (Opdenakker, 2006). The researcher planned to record the audio conversation to use the response for the research.

3.4 Data Analysis (Thematic analysis)

Thematic analysis was chosen as the data analysis method for this study because it is a rigorous qualitative methodology that allows for a thorough investigation of the interview data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The transcription of the audio recordings began the process, assuring accurate depiction of the participant's stories. Thematic analysis entails a step-by-step movement through numerous stages. The first stage was to immerse yourself in the data to become thoroughly familiar with its content, allowing you to appreciate the subtleties and complexity of participant's perspectives on chatbot interactions and brand engagement.

Following that, the data was rigorously coded to discover important parts linked to participant's experiences, views, and perceptions. This coding procedure revealed emerging patterns and repeating themes, allowing the creation of a rich and multi-dimensional representation of the data. These themes were subsequently improved and enhanced through an iterative review, debate, and interpretation process to guarantee their correctness and applicability. (Braun & Clarke, 2012). The discovered themes were validated in the following stage by comparing them to the original transcripts to ensure that they were consistent with the participants' real expressions. A deep and nuanced understanding of the complex relationships between Chabot interactions and consumer-brand engagement in the context of the UK retail industry is provided by the research use of theme analysis, which distils the essence of participants subjective judgements.

3.5 Ethical Consideration

The study followed ethical rules to protect participants' well-being and privacy. Participants were guaranteed confidentiality, and all data was anonymized throughout analysis and reporting. Participants provided informed consent and were told about their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Participants were informed and ensured that the audio recordings will not be shared with anyone and will be destroyed at the end of the study.

4.0. FINDINGS

Chatbots effect on customer satisfaction levels compared to traditional customer service channels

The most British example is probably the UK retail sector, where chatbots for major stores such as ASOS, HM, or Zara have proven to provide significant improvements in brand engagement metrics. Again, though, there are different degrees of success. Grocery retailers such as Asda or Tesco are leveraging chatbots for their stores to help customers with enquiries, including information about product availability, tracking of deliveries, locations etc.

One of the respondent further argued that “These chatbots are mostly a success as they enhance customer satisfaction and decrease waiting periods, despite the fact that the interactions are often more functional than conversational. On the other hand, fashion retailers like ASOS or HM are leveraging chatbots for shopping – either recommending styles, or tracking of orders – which means that interaction is more personalised, and overall engagement metrics and even conversion rates can rise as customers are more connected and guided throughout the process.”

“.....Retailers of consumer electronics and household goods, such as Currys and Argos, deploy chatbots to provide product information and troubleshooting, as well as after-sales service, bolstering consumers’ confidence in the brand and increasing post-purchase engagement. Specialist retailers of products such as beauty goods (Boots), craft products (Hobbycraft), and home furnishings (IKEA) turn to chatbots to answer highly specific product questions and make personalised recommendations, all of which should drive engagement as consumers demand these niche services.”

In sum, when designed to be fast, accurate and personalised, AI-powered chatbots have a huge impact on customer retention, satisfaction and conversion rates. It’s no surprise that many chatbots on the market today boast higher-quality and more entertaining interactions than many humans can offer. This type of chatbot, custom-built for fashion and other specialty retail, provides an experience that is an entirely new way to learn and interact with a brand. It tends to result in increased engagement and long-term loyalty, delivering a clear return on the retailer’s investment in state-of-the-art chatbot technology.

The relationship between the use of chatbots and changes in brand loyalty metrics

Businesses in the digital age are always looking for new and creative methods to interact with their clientele and build brand loyalty. In recent years, chatbots have become a popular technology. One of the respondents stated that “Metrics measuring brand loyalty, such as chance of referrals and repeat purchases, may be greatly impacted by the employment of chatbots. Customers are more likely to make repeat purchases and refer the company to others when they have a favorable experience with it through the usage of Chabot’s, such as effective problem-solving and personalized suggestions.” Furthermore, another respondent also argued that “Chatbots may be quite helpful in increasing the possibility that consumers would tell others about the business. Customers who believe their interactions with a Chabot were helpful, efficient, and personalized are more likely to share their positive experience with friends, family, and colleagues. This word-of-mouth recommendation may be a major generator of brand loyalty, resulting in higher client retention and acquisition in the long run.” The utilization of Chabot’s improves brand loyalty indicators such as repeat purchases and likely to refer the business. Businesses may strengthen their consumer connections and boost their chances of loyalty by facilitating personalized and efficient conversations with Chabots.

Chabot’s contribution in fostering emotional connections with users

Chabot’s are AI-powered tools that replicate human communication, providing users with a personalized and engaging experience. One of the primary advantages of chatbots is their capacity to establish emotional relationships with users in many ways. One of the respondents argued that “..., By responding immediately to questions and difficulties, chatbots may improve the user experience. This real-time engagement fosters a sensation of being heard and understood, resulting in a more favourable emotional connection with the user. Users frequently experience empathy from chatbots when they receive personalised and relevant replies.”

Another respondent claimed that “In order to customise customer’s replies based on the user emotional state, chatbots can also employ emotional intelligence. For example, a chatbot can recognise frustration or upset in a person and reply with empathy and understanding. This tailored approach can assist create trust and deepen the emotional link between the user and the chatbot. Furthermore, chatbots can improve user engagement by fostering a realistic and human-like conversational environment. Chatbots may establish a rapport and sense of connection with users by utilizing language that is both kind and engaging, resulting in a more favorable emotional experience.” Chatbots play an important role in creating emotional relationships with users by responding quickly, enabling personalized interactions, and communicating empathically. Understanding and responding to users’ emotional needs allows chatbots to offer a more engaging and rewarding experience, thereby deepening the user-brand tie.

5.0 DISCUSSION

The instant personalization chatbots have enabled in customer service and brand engagement has fundamentally changed the nature of consumer interactions. In this discussion, I highlight the influence of chatbots over some key factors such as customer satisfaction rates, brand loyalty behaviours, bonding emotions between them and how it enhanced among users, as well impact on different type of brand engagement metrics particularly in the UK retail businesses. Using a type of thematic analysis, this report extracts repeat themes across the domains to provide insight on where chatbots lay in the conversation.

As stated earlier, customer satisfaction, trust, and commitment are the three main drivers of customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction is a crucial predictor in fostering the retention of customers. At the same time, customer satisfaction influences customer trust, which both affect customer commitment. In turn, customer loyalty has a significant relation with profitability and is therefore highly relevant for every organization. To satisfy the customers and raise the organization’s overall customer satisfaction, a good customer experience is necessary.

Therefore, customer experience is during this study seen as a predictor of customer satisfaction, which is in line with multiple selected studies during the literature review search process (Jenneboer, L., Herrando, C., and Constantinides, E, 2022).

5.1. How Chatbots Are Influencing Customer Satisfaction?

➤ *Efficiency and Access*

As chatbots give instant responses to customer inquiries and operate 24/7, they are far more efficient and accessible than the most traditional customer support channels. This 24/7 availability diminishes the wait time while solving everyday problems of your customers and this results in an elevated customer satisfaction level. Issue resolution speed is another factor that very much affects the brand experience when it comes to customer support service – as customers like fast solutions to their problems (Xu, Shieh, Esch, & Ling, 2020).

➤ *Uniformity in dealing with Answers*

Unlike human agents, who can provide inconsistent responses due to personal differences or differing levels of training, chatbots deliver uniform responses. This consistency basically means that a user can expect to get the same information and therefore be more confident of the knowledge they have accumulated leading to trust.

➤ ***Taking Personal Ownership***

In contrast to the fact that at its core they are more automated than conversational, advanced chatbots use AI and machine learning so that conversations can be personalized using customer data and previous interactions. This level of personalization breathes life into customers and ultimately makes them feel cared for and heard, which directly or indirectly influences their customer satisfaction rates. Yet, it will forever be a challenge since no matter how complex our chatbots become — they still offer a limited amount of personalization compared to human interactions and some matters that are more emotional-based or deep, can simply not fit the bill.

5.2. Correlation between the introduction of chatbots and changes in brand loyalty

➤ ***Brand Loyalty and Chatbots***

Efficient and reliable chatbot interactions will increase customer's likelihood to recommend a brand. Because a happy customer is far more likely to make word-of-mouth nods (and that is how you win loyalty). Great service bots can improve NPS (Net Promoter Scores) by contributing to a better brand experience.

➤ ***Repeat Purchases***

Chatbots are a great way to indirectly promote repeat purchase and make the shopping process quicker. Chatbots, as an instance, can provide custom designed product tips, simplify the acquisition method and supply guide after income assistance. These are features that simply make it easier for a customer to return to the same brand/manufacturer for their future purchases, building up brand loyalty.

5.3. Emotional Bonds and Chatbots

➤ ***Human Interaction Emulation***

This led to the development of chatbots, which could create human-like experiences and form emotional connections fast among users — sort of like a virtual millennial campfire. Natural language processing and sentiment analysis capabilities make chatbots able to hold more human like, conversational communications. This function establishes an intimate connection between the user and the brand, a source of emotional bonds.

➤ ***Community Building***

Build community — Chatbots can also be used to manage online forums or social media groups where users engage with each other. Meanwhile, chatbots can share information relevant to the audience during this time and moderate discussions — even join in. A sense of community being part of a subgroup with shared interest and experience — drives user- to-user engagement even more because it gives people something to bond over beyond the chatbot in question.

5.4. UK Retail — Brand Engagement Metrics

➤ *Higher Interaction Rates*

Across the UK retail sector, chatbots have reported many fold increase interaction rates. Retail chatbots provide appropriate product information to a consumer, help them navigate through the store or answer their customer service query and this leads to enhanced engagement. This kind of escalated interaction is one measure of brand engagement because it shows a customer touching the brands digital platforms.

➤ *Friendly Experience*

Chatbots improve the customer experience by enabling seamless and efficient service. That increase in size shows improvements in customer satisfaction scores, even better customer reviews overall leading to other brand engagement metrics captured. UK-based retailers have said that customers who interact with chatbots tend to have a more favorable opinion of the brand, and this increases their engagement levels.

➤ *Data-Driven Insights*

Chatbots derive meaningful data regarding customer interaction and preference. In this way, retailers are able to develop a closer relationship with the needs of their customers through studies on how people interact and tailor their marketing strategy. This type of targeted activity will result in more efficient engagement campaigns which ultimately yield higher conversion figures — surveying the full extent to which chatbots have a far-reaching impact upon brand engagement metrics.

5.5. How it Stands Up Against Traditional Customer Support Channels

➤ *Cost Efficiency*

A second cheaper option is to use chatbots, as they cost more money. While the first investment in chatbot technology could be costly, resulting operational costs savings over the long term are huge. Chatbots, unlike human agents, do not need wages, benefits or training and can work multiple inquiries at a time without additional costs. This can help save significant on costs, which brands should be looking to instead spend elsewhere in customer experience and satisfaction.

➤ *Scalability*

Chatbots have a clear edge regarding this aspect compared to traditional customer support. The volume of customer inquiries increases as a brand grows requiring more support resources. That allows chatbots to scale up with the growth of our business without requiring us to hire hundreds more support agents. This scalability reinforces the ability for customer support to be consistent and reliable regardless of inquiry volume.

➤ *Constraints on Complexity of Interactions*

Since a lot of contexts are complex and involve emotionally sensitive interactions, chatbots imply can do this right now. Authenticity requires empathy and nuanced understanding, which a human agent is trained to provide for more complicated problems or when dealing with distressed customers. That means for many use cases, chatbots are excellent because they fast and scalable but only complementary to purely human customer support.

Overall, thematic analysis supports the conventional wisdom that chatbots have a positive effect on user experience and brand loyalty, suggesting it led to improvement of various customer satisfaction and brand metrics specifically in UK retail sector. Chatbots, on the one hand, improve customer support efficiency by providing speed to resolve issues and consistency in answering questions — both are critical aspects of keeping consumers happy. They help in keeping your clients loyal to your brand which on the other hand assists in repeat purchases and word of mouth creation. Instead, they serve a role in creating emotional ties with clients or prospects through human-like interaction and efforts to build their own community. Chatbots offer a highly interactive form of brand engagement which boosts click-through rate and chat bots remain one of the best customer experience tools that help in driving valuable data-insight.

6.0 CONCLUSION

This study examined the role of chatbots as conversational agents in enhancing consumer brand engagement in the UK retail industry. Through a qualitative analysis of consumer experiences and perceptions, it was found that chatbots significantly influence customer satisfaction, loyalty, and emotional connection with brands. Chatbots efficiency, availability, and personalized interactions contribute to higher customer satisfaction levels compared to traditional customer service channels. Additionally, chatbots play a crucial role in fostering brand loyalty by facilitating repeat purchases and encouraging positive word-of-mouth recommendations.

The study also highlighted the capacity of chatbots to build emotional connections with users through empathetic and personalized communication, which enhances overall brand engagement. Various UK retail sectors, including fashion, grocery, electronics, and specialty retail, have successfully leveraged chatbots to improve customer interactions and engagement metrics. However, the research identified several limitations, including potential biases in qualitative data, a narrow focus on specific communication styles, and the rapidly evolving nature of chatbot technology. Future research should address these limitations by incorporating quantitative methods, exploring a wider range of communication styles, and conducting comparative studies across different regions and industries.

In conclusion, chatbots present a promising tool for retailers aiming to enhance customer engagement and loyalty. As technology continues to advance, ongoing research and adaptation will be essential to fully harness the potential of chatbots in the retail industry and beyond.

7.0 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Despite the insightful findings of this study, there are several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the study reliance on qualitative data from telephone interviews may introduce biases related to self-reporting and the subjective interpretation of chatbot interactions. Additionally, the sample size and demographic scope, though diverse, may not comprehensively represent the entire UK retail consumer base. Future research should consider employing a mixed-methods approach, incorporating quantitative data to enhance the generalizability and robustness of the findings.

Secondly, the study focused on two specific communication styles (task-oriented and social-oriented), potentially overlooking other relevant styles or hybrid approaches that could influence brand engagement. Future studies should explore a broader range of communication styles and their impacts on different aspects of consumer behavior. Another limitation is the fast-evolving nature of chatbot technology.

The study findings may quickly become outdated as AI and machine learning advancements lead to more sophisticated and human-like chatbots. Continuous research is necessary to keep up with these technological developments and their implications for brand engagement. Finally, while the study provides valuable insights into the UK retail industry, it does not consider other geographic regions or industries, which may have different consumer behaviors and expectations. Future research should aim to compare the impact of chatbots across various markets and sectors to develop a more comprehensive understanding of their effectiveness.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adamopoulou, E., and Moussiades, L. (2020). An overview of chatbot technology. In: *Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI)*. Cham: Springer, pp. 373-383.
- [2] Alibaba.com, 2023. Unlocking the Full Potential of Retail Chatbots. Alibaba.com Reads. Available at: <https://reads.alibaba.com> [Accessed 21 September 2024].
- [3] Bock, D. E., Wolter, J. S., & Ferrell, O. C. (2020). Artificial intelligence: Disrupting what we know about services. *The Journal of services marketing*, 34(3), 317-334.
- [4] Braun Virginia & Clarke Victoria. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235356393_Using_thematic_analysis_in_psychology.
- [5] Braun Virginia & Clarke Victoria. (2012). Thematic analysis. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269930410_Thematic_analysis.
- [6] Chen, J.-S., Le, T.-T.-Y., & Florence, D. (2021). Usability and responsiveness of artificial intelligence chatbot on online customer experience in e-retailing. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*.
- [7] Flick, U., 2014. In: *An introduction to qualitative research*. 5th edition ed. London: SAGE Publications.
- [8] Hussain, S., Sianaki, O.A., and Ababneh, N., 2019. A survey on conversational agents/chatbots classification and design techniques. In: *Proceedings of the 2019 2nd International Conference on Machine Learning and Intelligent Systems (MLIS)*. ACM, pp.109–115.
- [9] Jenneboer, L., Herrando, C., and Constantinides, E. 2022. "The Impact of Chatbots on Customer Loyalty: A Systematic Literature Review" *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research* 17, no. 1: 212-229. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer17010011>.
- [10] Khanna, A., Pandey, B., Vashishta, K., Kalia, K., Pradeepkumar, B., & Das, T. (2015). A study of today's ai through chatbots and rediscovery of machine intelligence. *International Journal of u-and e-Service, Science and Technology*, 8(7), 277-284.
- [11] Leedy PD, Ormrod. J., 2005. *Planning and Design*. In: *Practical Research*. 8th ed. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [12] Mende, M., Scott, M. L., van Doorn, J., Grewal, D., & Shanks, I. (2019). Service robots rising: How humanoid robots influence service experiences and elicit compensatory consumer responses. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 56(4), 535-556.
- [13] Nguyen, M. H. (2020). The latest market research, trends, and landscape in the growing AI chatbot industry. *Business Insider*. Retrieved from: <https://www.businessinsider.com/chatbot-market-stats-trends?r=AU&IR=T>
- [14] Olmez, M. (2018). How to use AI in e-commerce. *Accenture*. Retrieved from: <https://www.accenture.com/nl-en/blogs/insights/how-to-use-ai-in-e-commerce>.

- [15] Opendakker, Raymond. (2006). Advantages and Disadvantages of Four Interview Techniques in Qualitative Research. Retrieved from:
- [16] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/48666088_Advantages_and_Disadvantages_of_Four_Interview_Techniques_in_Qualitative_Research_Electronic_Journal.
- [17] Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1988). SERVQUAL: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), 12.
- [18] Sangroya, Amit & Saini, Pratik & Anantaram, Chandrasekhar. (2017). Chatbot as an Intermediary between a Customer and the Customer Care Ecosystem. 128-133. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324072601_Chatbot_as_an_Intermediary_between_a_Customer_and_the_Customer_Care_Ecosystem
- [19] Rajasekar, S. Philominathan, P. & Chinnathambi, V. (2013). RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. Retrieved at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/physics/0601009.pdf#:~:text=Research%20methodology%20is%20a%20systematic,phenomena%20are%20called%20research%20methodology>.
- [20] Ryan, G., 2018. Introduction to positivism, interpretivism and critical theory. *Nurse Researcher*, 25(4), pp. 41-49.
- [21] Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A., (2007). *Research Methods for Business Students*. 4th edition ed. Edinburgh Gate, Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall.
- [22] Vijayakumar, M. (2024). A Study on Chatbots and Virtual Assistants in Customer Engagement: A Review. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, 14(1), 204-208.
- [23] Xu, Y., Shieh, C.-H., van Esch, P., & Ling, I. L. (2020). AI customer service: Task complexity, problem-solving ability, and usage intention. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 28(4), 189-199.
- [24] Webretailer, 2024. Chatbots in Retail: Enhancing Efficiency and Customer Engagement. Webretailer. Available at: <https://www.webretailer.com> [Accessed 21 September 2024].
- [25] Xu, Y., Shieh, C.-H., van Esch, P., & Ling, I. L. (2020). AI customer service: task complexity, problem-solving ability, and usage intention. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 28(4), 189-199.

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